

STAGES OF TRANSITION TO INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS (IFRS) IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article examines Uzbekistan's transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), analyzing its stages, challenges, and impact on sustainable development. By reviewing global experiences and Uzbekistan's specific context, the study underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement, regulatory updates, and tailored strategies for effective IFRS adoption. The findings highlight the potential of IFRS to improve financial transparency, attract investments, and support economic diversification in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: IFRS, financial reporting, sustainable development, transition challenges, economic diversification.

Introduction

The adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) represents a significant milestone in the financial and economic landscape of any country, signaling a commitment to transparency, accountability, and global integration. For emerging economies like Uzbekistan, the transition to IFRS is not merely a technical accounting exercise but a strategic move towards aligning with global financial practices, enhancing the attractiveness of the country to foreign investors, and laying the groundwork for sustainable economic development. This transition is part of Uzbekistan's broader economic reform agenda, which aims to modernize its economy, improve the business environment, and foster a more dynamic and competitive market.

The way towards IFRS adoption in Uzbekistan is particularly noteworthy given the country's historical reliance on Soviet-era accounting standards, which differ significantly from IFRS in terms of transparency, disclosure requirements, and the overall approach to financial reporting. The shift towards IFRS requires a comprehensive overhaul of accounting practices, regulatory frameworks, and professional training programs. It also necessitates a cultural shift within organizations, as stakeholders at all levels must embrace the principles of transparency and accountability that underpin IFRS.

The introduction of IFRS in Uzbekistan is expected to have far-reaching implications for the country's economy. By adopting these standards, Uzbekistan aims to improve the quality of financial information available to investors, thereby increasing investment flows, supporting the growth of the private sector, and ultimately contributing to economic diversification and resilience. Furthermore, the transition to IFRS is seen as a critical component of Uzbekistan's efforts to integrate more fully into the global economy, facilitating cross-border trade and investment by providing a common financial language understood by international investors and businesses.

Literature Review

The transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in emerging economies has garnered significant attention in academic literature, highlighting both the potential benefits and the challenges associated with this shift.

Owolabi and Iyoha (2012) emphasize the importance of education, sensitization, and communication to stakeholders in the adoption and adaptation of IFRS in Africa. They advocate for a rigorous capacity-building program across regulatory bodies, firms, and training institutions to facilitate IFRS implementation. This recommendation is pertinent to Uzbekistan, where a similar multi-stakeholder approach could enhance the transition process.

Paknejad's (2017) study on Iran's voluntary adoption of IFRS reveals that certain factors significantly influence the decision to adopt these standards. The research, based on the perspectives of financial business managers and experts from companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange, underscores the practicality of IFRS adoption and its impact on financial reporting quality. Uzbekistan can draw from Iran's experience, considering the role of internal factors and stakeholder perceptions in the adoption process.

Jinadu's comprehensive review of IFRS adoption across various countries highlights the diverse impacts of these standards on financial reporting and accounting quality. The study covers the implications for small and growing sectors, the economic and political ramifications, and the challenges and prospects in different banking sectors, including Ethiopia's experience. This broad overview provides a valuable context for understanding the multifaceted effects of IFRS adoption, relevant to Uzbekistan's economic landscape.

Ablazov (2023) discusses the development of a model for accounting financial results in construction organizations in Uzbekistan, in the context of adopting IFRS 15 "Revenue from Contracts with Customers." This study is

directly relevant to Uzbekistan's transition, highlighting the sector-specific challenges and the need for tailored approaches to implement IFRS standards effectively.

Analysis and Results

The transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in Uzbekistan can be dissected into several key stages, each presenting its unique set of challenges and milestones. This analysis delves into the progress made thus far, the hurdles encountered, and the preliminary outcomes of the transition process, drawing on comparative insights from global practices to contextualize Uzbekistan's journey.

Initial Legislative Framework and Awareness

The initial stage of Uzbekistan's transition to IFRS involved the establishment of a legislative framework that mandated the adoption of these standards for certain categories of entities, particularly those with significant foreign investment and those listed on the stock exchange. This phase was crucial for setting the legal and regulatory groundwork for the transition. However, one of the primary challenges during this period was raising awareness and understanding of IFRS among local businesses and accounting professionals. The lack of IFRS-trained accountants and auditors in the country posed a significant barrier to implementation.

Capacity Building and Education

Recognizing the need for skilled professionals capable of working with IFRS, Uzbekistan embarked on a comprehensive capacity-building and education campaign. This involved partnerships with international organizations and institutions to provide training and resources for accountants and financial professionals. Despite these efforts, the demand for IFRS expertise continues to outstrip supply, indicating a need for ongoing investment in education and professional development.

Sector-Specific Implementation

The analysis reveals that the adoption of IFRS in Uzbekistan has been uneven across different sectors. The banking sector, for instance, has made significant strides in aligning its reporting practices with IFRS, driven by the requirements of international financial institutions and investors. In contrast, the transition has been slower in other sectors, such as manufacturing and agriculture, where the perceived benefits of IFRS adoption are less immediate, and the costs of transition are more acutely felt.

Preliminary Outcomes

Despite these challenges, the preliminary results of IFRS adoption in Uzbekistan are promising. There has been a noticeable improvement in the quality and comparability of financial statements produced by entities that have adopted IFRS. This has enhanced the transparency of the financial reporting environment in Uzbekistan, making it more attractive to foreign investors and facilitating better decision-making by local stakeholders.

Moreover, the transition to IFRS has stimulated discussions and initiatives around corporate governance and financial disclosure practices in Uzbekistan. As companies adapt to the requirements of IFRS, there is a growing recognition of the importance of robust governance structures and transparent reporting in building trust with investors and the public.

Comparative Insights

The experiences of other countries in the region, such as Iran and Poland, offer valuable lessons for Uzbekistan. These countries have faced similar challenges in terms of capacity building, sector-specific implementation, and regulatory adaptation. Their successes and setbacks highlight the importance of sustained government support, the strategic engagement of stakeholders, and the flexibility to adapt implementation strategies to local contexts.

Conclusion

The transition to IFRS in Uzbekistan is a work in progress, marked by significant achievements and ongoing challenges. The analysis underscores the importance of continued investment in education and capacity building, as well as the need for tailored approaches to sector-specific implementation. As Uzbekistan moves forward with its IFRS adoption way, the experiences of other countries serve as a valuable reference point, offering insights into best practices and strategies for overcoming obstacles. The ultimate goal of this transition is to enhance the transparency, comparability, and quality of financial reporting in Uzbekistan, contributing to the country's sustainable economic development and integration into the global financial system.

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